

Implementation and Validation Approach of the C-ITS novel solution proposed by SAFE STRIP for self-explanatory and forgiving infrastructures

Maria Gkemou
Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)
Centre for Research and Technology
Hellas (CERTH)
Thessaloniki, Greece
mgemou@certh.gr

Ioannis Gkragkopoulou
Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)
Centre for Research and Technology
Hellas (CERTH)
Thessaloniki, Greece
igragop@certh.gr

Evangelos Bekiaris
Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)
Centre for Research and Technology
Hellas (CERTH)
Thessaloniki, Greece
abek@certh.gr

Andrea Steccanella
EMEA Product Development -
Electrical / Electronics – Safety &
Driver Assistance Systems
CRF S.C.p.A.
Trento, Italy
andrea.steccanella@crf.it

Dionysios Kehagias
Information Technologies Institute
Centre for Research and Technology
Hellas (CERTH)
Thessaloniki, Greece
diok@iti.gr

Abstract – Proven positive effects of Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) are in many cases prohibited by the non-negligible cost required for the initial installation but also maintenance of the infrastructure and the on-board vehicle intelligent systems that need to be deployed for their operation. In parallel, a series of State of the Art cooperative safety and automated solutions do not exploit data directly originating from the infrastructure and the environment, failing, in this way, to have the most reliable possible safety critical information that is vital to the optimum fulfillment of their objectives; that being primarily the increase of traffic safety. SAFE STRIP (SAFE and green Sensor Technologies for self-explaining and forgiving Road Interactive applications) EU funded project envisions to simultaneously address those challenges by introducing a revolutionary C-ITS approach through the placement of low-cost innovative sensorial frameworks on the road pavement surface itself in order to acquire reliable and lane specific traffic and environmental information that is directed through I2X (Infrastructure to Everything) communication to all types of vehicles. The current manuscript presents the vision and objectives, the core use cases serving as the proof of concept of the technological solution built, the implementation approach towards delivering the solution and, finally, the multilayered validation approach anticipated by the Consortium towards delivering a prototype of an as much as possible high technological readiness as well as C-ITS functions evidencing its value.

Keywords - C-ITS, self-explanatory and forgiving infrastructures, automation, micro and nano sensors, I2X, on-road – unit, energy harvesting, validation of C-ITS

I. INTRODUCTION

According to most recent reports [1], the maximum penetration rates of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) in Europe did not surpass 9.86% in 2014. Thus, although Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) may have a great impact on road safety, traffic efficiency and comfort, their extremely small penetration practically nullifies their impact. That is basically due to pricing, and, in specific, among other, due to the very high cost of applying the infrastructure required in many cases for cooperative applications functioning; let alone the cost

required to support automated driving functions. Still, critical infrastructure situations (such as night and bad weather, no information for road surface condition) represent 35% of the root causes for road injury accidents in EU (TRACE 2015). Also, the Motorcycle Accident In-Depth Study (MAIDS) showed that 4.2% of the investigated Powered Two Wheelers (PTW) accidents (Total n=921) occurred in a motorway. Road condition was described as “wet” in 7.9% of all collected cases. Water was coded as a roadway contamination, because of the negative effect that it could have upon PTW handling and braking capabilities. Ice, snow and mud were reported in 2.5% of all cases. These findings illustrate the effect of roadway contamination risks in PTW accidents. Surface deterioration or damaged bitumen (i.e. broken or separated asphalt) was found on 26% of all roadways. Thus, it is implied that road conditions and wear should be clearly considered in advanced road safety systems. On the other hand, accident reduction cost due to application of Variable Speed Limit (VSL) at intersections/merging links is reported to be from 30% to 40% (Lind 2009). Benefits are in terms of safety, traffic efficiency and time gains, as seen from a typical VMS application in Sweden. However, as they are costly (~ 24-90 K€ each), they are not widely applied in European highways.

In order to meet the aforementioned challenges, a revolutionary C-ITS technological solution is introduced in the context of the SAFE STRIP H2020 EU funded project (GA: 723211; starting on 1st of May 2017; <http://safestrip.eu/>), that shifts intelligence from the vehicle to the road infrastructure, in a cost-efficient way, deploying micro/nano sensorial frameworks, Infrastructure to Vehicle (I2V)/ Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I) communication technologies as well as energy harvesting to support the implementation of custom low-cost on-road strips that will be installed in each lane of the road pavement and will finally be painted by commercial paint provided by SWARCO (project beneficiary), reaching a height of 9mm from the pavement surface.

The on-road strips, through a communication gateway, will transmit real-time information (static and dynamic) about the road condition, the traffic and the environmental conditions to the equipped and non-equipped vehicles supporting a series of C-ITS functions with reliable, accurate and lane specific information, directly coming from the infrastructure, that will be further personalised and supported through a negotiations-based Human Machine Interface (HMI).

The vision is to make roads self-explanatory (with personalised in-vehicle messages) and forgiving (due to advanced cooperative functions) for all road users (trucks, cars and vulnerable road users, such as PTW's riders) and all vehicle generations (non-equipped, C-ITS equipped, autonomous), with reduced maintenance cost, full recyclability and added value services, as well as supporting real-time predictive road maintenance functions. All vehicles generations will benefit; C-ITS equipped vehicles through upgrade of their intelligence, non-equipped vehicles will benefit from intelligent functions that lacked before and autonomous vehicles will acquire lane localization data that will assist them fulfilling the gaps of on-board systems for the creation of virtual lanes, corridors, etc. that are essential to them. Infrastructure operators as well as all road users (passenger cars, PTW's – Powered Two Wheelers, buses, trucks) are supported, while benefits for Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) are also essential. Most importantly, however, the most important contribution of SAFE STRIP lies in the vision to replace mainstream surveillance systems, VMS and toll stations through its proposed solution, which implies a radical reduction of installation and maintenance costs with a parallel increase of traffic safety.

The current manuscript describes in short the implementation objectives (section II), the Use Cases reflecting the C-ITS functions that aim to serve as a proof of concept of the integrated technological solution section (III), proceeds with the synopsis of the implementation approach (section IV) and its validation approach (section V) to conclude with the next steps and challenges anticipated (section VI).

II. THE OBJECTIVES

The overall miniaturised road platform to be developed, consisting of all sensorial, communication and energy harvesting elements placed at the infrastructure side, should be in position to:

- Embed static info (i.e. enhanced map data, speed limit, curvature, asphalt characteristics, etc.) to be transmitted to the vehicles, programmed after deployment and reprogrammed when the use of the road changes.
- Receive dynamic info (e.g. from TMC – Traffic Management Centre messages), process and transmit them to the passing vehicles, to be offered to the driver/rider in a personalised manner.
- Measure dynamic environmental parameters (i.e. temperature, humidity, ice, gas, ambient light) and accurately estimate each vehicle's dynamic friction coefficient (through road sensors data fusion with vehicles' intelligent tyres' info).
- Sense passing vehicles, including non-equipped ones, measure the transit time, speed and lateral position in the

lane, provide basic classification of the vehicle type and, thus, offer key road load & circulation data to the TMC.

- Sense pedestrian crossings, work zones, railway crossings and other critical areas and warn the driver/rider well ahead of them.
- Enable high accuracy and low cost automatic parking/tolling/insurance policies.
- Define and manage lane-level virtual corridors for automated driving.

III. THE USE CASES

The supported C-ITS functions that serve as a proof of concept of the SAFE STRIP integrated solutions are reflected through the project Use Cases (UCs). Those have been fully defined upon a user centered methodology, as depicted in Fig. 1. The starting and reference point has been the original goals of the project, and specifically that part encompassing the target applications that will serve as proof of concept of the implementation approach towards the integrated solution as well as the need that led to the emergence of SAFE STRIP overall. Those have been investigated, revisited and analysed in the context. More particularly, the revisiting groundwork relied on the consolidation of all relevant stakeholders needs, views and priorities, as those have been captured through the outputs of 431 from 10 countries respondents participating in on-line and in-depth surveys, the investigation of relevant accidents/incidents and gaps/priorities from the infrastructure point of view based on literature, the investigation on the legal/operational limitations on infrastructure end based on study of relevant Directives and the Consortium experts' views. The next step was the critical review and prioritisation of them by experts participating in a Pan-European workshop and the Scientific Advisory Board of the project.

Fig. 1. SAFE STRIP User – Centred Iterative Approach.

The output has been an aggregated collection of gaps, restrictions, needs, views and priorities that has led to the extraction of the UCs. The UCs were described in such a detail to serve as functional requirements checklists feeding the system architecture and specifications work, the implementation work and the issue of pilot plans and validation approach. In the context of planned validation activities of the project (technical validation and user trials), conducted in 4 rounds, each iteration round will lead to an optimisation period that will, in turn, may lead to UCs revisions.

Finally, 9 UCs clusters have been determined for the proof of concept of SAFE STRIP technological solution, encompassing several functions each, as follows:

- **UC1: Virtual Cooperative safety function**, which intends to upgrade the two virtual safety functions “Virtual VRU protection” and “Wrong Way Driving”, already available in equipped vehicles. The first one is exploiting the ability of the strip to detect position and speed of vehicles and of VRU at zebra crossing, providing application for a) the position and speed, at lane level, for all vehicles in relation to pedestrian crossing location removing the need to use precise GPS positioning system, b) the presence of VRU close or on the zebra crossing in term of magnitude and direction of speed and c) information of the road surface conditions such as friction and wear. The second application, matches a respective application for equipped vehicles. The system detects all vehicles that are driving in the wrong direction and dispatches a warning to all other vehicles approaching the critical area.
- **UC2: Enhanced Cooperative safety function.** Same as UC1, but for equipped vehicles. The two anticipated applications are being reflected in two distinct UCs as the implementation path differs significantly for equipped and non-equipped vehicles.
- **UC3: Road wear level and predictive road maintenance.** By measuring pavement strains the motorway operator can evaluate pavement response and cracking performance. Using the present pavement condition and the latest rehabilitation action performed the remaining service life and the average service life of pavements can be obtained. Also, the critical values and types of pavement damage (for road safety) are defined so as to feed prompt mitigation from the infrastructure maintenance departments and in-time notification to drivers/riders through VMS.
- **UC4: Rail crossing and road works safety function.** Road works and railway crossings are critical sections with regard to safety, where constraints to vehicle speed or position in specific lanes must be enforced. The applications for the two driving scenarios are based on the artificial co-driver concept which issues a warning when the estimated driver’s intention does not match the safest manoeuvre. Specifically, road work safety function detects at lane level approaching vehicles (equipped and non-equipped) and provides a warning if the speed is not properly adapted or the vehicle will not stop in time in case of traffic jam in the road work area. Additionally, based on vehicle’s lane position, lane change may be also suggested. Similarly, for railway crossing safety function, especially when unprotected, the function will generate a warning when the estimated driver’s intention does not match the safest manoeuvre to reduce the speed to the prescribed speed limit at the railway crossing or the vehicle will not be able to stop in case the train is approaching.
- **UC5: Merging and Intersection Support: e2Call.** The application is an enhancement of the e2Call safety function developed by CRF for equipped vehicles. The original application is purely based on V2V which relies on precise GPS positioning and intersection, roundabout or road merging maps (for road layout and geometry). The output of the application is a warning to the driver when a potential conflict with other vehicles at intersection may happen or is imminent or when the driver is going not to respect give way right, stop sign or traffic light red signal. SAFE STRIP will improve the performance of e2Call function in many ways: 1) by providing the position and speed at lane level for all vehicles, 2) by removing the need to use precise GPS positioning system, 3) by supplying the local digital map close to the intersection, 4) by providing information of the road surface conditions such as friction and wear, and 5) by providing info about the traffic jam.
- **UC6: Personalised VMS/VDS and Traffic Centre Information.** This application corresponds to the actual replacement of the current VMS/VDS infrastructure through a personalised to the driver/rider virtual VMS function, that though respecting the authorisation processes of the Traffic Management Centres (TMCs), aims to make redundant the typical VMS infrastructure.
- **UC7: Autonomous vehicles support**, for highway driving thanks to sensors data integration that is expected to lower the frequency of the driver having to take back control of the vehicle. Four (4) specific enhanced perception applications for automated vehicles will be supported, namely: *Dynamic trajectory estimation for automated vehicles*; *Definition of lane-level virtual corridors*; *Tollgates management* and *Work zones detection*.
- **UC8: Virtual Toll Collection - for non-autonomous vehicles.** A virtual toll application for non-autonomous vehicles will be developed aiming to replace current toll stations. The application will support toll station simulation enabling automatic passage as well as automatic payment.
- **UC9: Parking booking and charging.** Replacing the currently used surveillance smart parking infrastructure, the application optimises the use of available parking space. It provides information to the users about the availability and location of free parking lots, encompassing also payment. Two scenarios are considered, parking with numbered places and street parking (free of charge parking and regulated parking).

IV. IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

SAFE STRIP consists of diverse technologies and engineering processes closely collaborating towards achieving the overall goal. The overall high-level logical architecture of the SAFE STRIP technology is depicted in Fig. 2. The basic part of the SAFE STRIP miniaturised road platform is the On-Road Unit (ORU) platform, which essentially consists of a custom strip placed at specific points on the traffic lanes, as well as on the road pavement next to a zebra crossing area. The role of the ORU is to detect and transmit all intended data (vehicle/pedestrian detection, road condition, environmental data, etc.) to the Road Side Bridge (RSB). The On Road Unit (ORU) platform contains all necessary sensors requiring close-to-road or lane-specific measurements. It is based on a central unit, which drives several sensors, some of which being external to the ORU board, such as the Vehicle Detection and Identification System (VDIS) for vehicle detection and VRU detection and the gas nano sensors that is a custom system made by SAFE STRIP, that has been setup utilising ribbon switches and

RFID technology. In the case of non-equipped vehicles, Global Positioning System (GPS) is used for determining the position of the vehicle.

Fig. 2. SAFE STRIP functional architecture.

The ORU platform is powered by a global energy unit utilising rechargeable and non-rechargeable batteries and micro harvesters. Apart from the main ORU platform, the strip also encompasses two strain gauges per lane, placed at right angle to each other, to measure strain profile of the pavement. This is also connected to the RSB electronic board and powered by the power unit of the latest (due to its high power consumption).

The basic communication between the ORU and the RSB is realised wirelessly over Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE). The RSB is also able to communicate wirelessly through ETSI ITS-G5 with the equipped vehicles and through Long Term Evolution (LTE) network to the non-equipped vehicles respectively. Additionally, for low-speed scenarios (e.g. in the urban traffic environment), the RSB utilises Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technology in order to communicate with both the equipped and non-equipped vehicles. Furthermore, the RSB exploits LTE network in order to communicate with the Central ITS Station (C-ITS-S) of safe strip sending modified ITS messages. Upon the decision making process, a warning message is produced and is finally sent, as a Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) message, to the end-user mobile application that is specifically built for the non-equipped vehicle users. C-ITS-S stands for the SAFE STRIP sub-system being responsible for the provisioning of C-ITS services. It communicates with the road operator, traffic management and parking operator centres. C-ITS-S also interacts with non-equipped vehicles via LTE.

There are two approaches applied (and validated) for powering the RSB, one based on 100% powering from renewable energy sources with no need to be connected to the electrical grid. In this approach, the main challenge is to design the RSB in a way that the system does not run out of energy. In the second design approach, the RSB is powered at least 20% from renewable energy sources whilst another 80% from the electrical grid. In the latest approach, the RSB has to be connected to the electrical grid to charge its battery when it is not possible from the renewable sources. The

validation of both approaches is one of the objectives of the technical validation of the system.

The vehicle demonstrators of the project are equipped with an On-Board Unit (OBU), which integrates all the necessary communication modules and software stack for the realization of V2X communications and the required interfaces for the interconnection with vehicle's CAN bus system and sensors. The OBU implements a Decision Support System (DSS) that takes all input data and produces a warning message that is shown to the driver through the on-board warning system. This interaction is valid for equipped vehicles. In the case of non-equipped vehicles, decision making runs on the C-ITS-S.

The C-ITS-S Platform is able to integrate several ITS applications (e.g. Urban Traffic Control, Public Transport, Parking, Streetlights, VMS, etc.), independently of the supplier or technology; it elaborates data coming from the road, performs diagnostic analysis and provides C-ITS services. It has an interface based on MQTT for the provision of cooperative standard messages via LTE to the vehicles, RSBs and other users. It also has an interface based on web service for the exchange of cooperative messages with the mobility management centres. The provisioning of co-operative messages happens thanks to several co-operative messages manager that converts data coming from the different control centres into proper messages ready to be dispatched to vehicles. The co-operative messages managers will also manage the geo-dispatching of the information, and the management of the message validity, for example erasing from the message queue old information.

Whilst the equipped vehicles will receive information on-board, an end-user mobile application – specially addressing non-equipped vehicle users (including PTWs) - is developed as native application to support the latest Android and iOS versions. In both operating systems, the application will take advantage of all device capabilities (GPS, accelerometer) and will support multiple languages. The end-user mobile application will upload continuously to the C-ITS-S platform a number of specific important values (id, coordinates, speed, etc.) required from the C-ITS-S platform processing. The C-ITS-S platform will be responsible for storing this information (for historic purposes) and also process it. It then publishes the exported results by push back warnings/notifications/recommendations information to the end-user application. This message pushing is made available only to entities that have been assigned to this specific notification service (MQTT) of the C-ITS-S platform. Each entity (RSB, DSS, HMI, Co-Driver) is considered by the system as a software module. Each software module communicates each other via MQTT protocol. In the initial phase of development, the software modules will “run” on each partner’s site. If operational tests show unacceptable delays, installation at the same physical place/server will be considered.

V. VALIDATION APPROACH

A. Iterative and Incremental Validation

SAFE STRIP will be evaluated in controlled environments (test beds in Spain and in France and 2 closed test tracks in Italy) and real life conditions in 2 sites (A22 highway in Italy and ATTIKI ODOS in Greece) with 6 vehicle demonstrators in order to validate its performance, user experience and acceptance aspects and, finally, assess

its impacts to safety, mobility, the environment and European industrial competitiveness among other.

There will be 6 equipped demonstrators participating in the anticipated tests coming from project beneficiaries, namely: a FIAT – 500L (passenger car) from CRF; a VW – PASSAT (autonomous passenger car) provided by VALEO for the autonomous functions evaluation; a PIAGGIO MP3 (motorcycle - PTW) provided by PIAGGIO; a Renault Espace (passenger test vehicle) provided by CONTI (for the dynamic friction coefficient estimation); a Lancia – Thesis (passenger car) provided by CERTH/HIT and a PIAGGIO – MP3 Hybrid (motorcycle - PTW) provided by CERTH/HIT. An iterative implementation and validation plan is developed covering all types and phases of anticipated testing.

Fig. 3. SAFE STRIP User – Centred Iterative Approach.

As mentioned again, four (4) testing validation rounds have been planned in order to iteratively test and optimise the final solution. First validation round focus is on the testing of the first version of the ORU. At second stage – on top of the upgraded ORU’s elements - the communication channels are tested (i.e. how the information originating from the ORUs can reach the vehicles and the backend services). RSB is tested to allow the communication with ORUs, equipped vehicles (i.e. vehicles with ETSI ITS-G5 transceiver) and back-end services (C-ITS-S platform available as cloud service via cellular LTE connectivity). In addition, the first tests of HMI elements and strategies as well as the 1st stage of the friction coefficient benchmarking tests will take place in this phase, to feed the upcoming one. On the basis of the outcomes of the first two testing iterations, an enhanced and optimised version of the key modules of SAFE STRIP system will derive. In third iteration all the information gathered from the infrastructure and the vehicles will be fused and tested in the context of the SAFE STRIP UCs – turned to demonstration cases.

The aim of the project is to spread SAFE STRIP solution as much as possible; therefore, the project tackles different type of demonstrators: cars and motorcycles equipped with ETSI ITS-G5, non-equipped cars and motorcycles where cellular connectivity is available, autonomous cars and finally drivers with only smartphone applications available. Iteration 3 is dedicated to the assessment of the applications into these demonstrators in a homogenous way. This iteration is split into two sessions: the first one runs the final technical validation of the integrated system on all ends – infrastructure, application, communication and demonstrator ends, while the second one serves as the first round of user trials as explained in the following section.

Finally, the fourth round encompasses the final real-life trials of the project. SAFE STRIP will be deployed in the anticipated test sites. The ORU’s will be encapsulated and integrated in SWARCO tapes on-site emulating the anticipated real-life deployment of the system. An intense testing campaign with drivers and riders will run in test tracks and highways to validate the performance of the system, the overall customer acceptance, the expected impact and potential of SAFE STRIP.

B. Technical Validation Approach

Technical validation, anticipated prior to real life user testing, is multilayered and incremental. The testing iterations have been considered in such a way so that the system grows in complexity iteration by iteration in a controlled way. At high level all the components are structured in two layers: “Single module” and “Application module”. Four different actors have been identified in the project: ORU, RSB, Demonstrators (divided into EqVeh standing for equipped vehicles and NoEqVeh standing for non-equipped vehicles) and the Backend services. Each of them is composed by single components (or basic functionalities) data of which are being fused to develop the SAFE STRIP applications or services: generate warnings or collect statistical data for backend services (advanced functionalities). In Fig.4 the layers of each actor are distinguished: yellow containers represent the single modules, modules that shall be tested as independent components, while the red ones represent the application layer (the advanced functionalities of the specific actor). ORU and RSB are totally new components; therefore an assessment phase was deemed necessary to be performed to validate the proper operation in real-life conditions. During the first iteration, the technology limitations of the selected sensors are assessed and the quality/reliability of the retrieved data. Additional complexity comes from the energy constraints, as ORUs should be able to operate without external power supply for at least one year operation and RSB should be able to minimise the energy request from the power grid in the optimum case). ORU will be placed directly on the road surface. Therefore, and prior to the industrial paint application, specific encapsulation has been developed for application to protect the electronics from physical damages (extremely high or low temperature, presence of corrosive materials, heavy vehicles passing over, etc.). For the preliminary testing, the encapsulated solution is tested without electrical components in the second iteration while the complete prototype is tested for the first time during the third iteration.

Fig. 4. SAFE STRIP incremental technical validation process.

C. Infrastructure deployment

The SAFE STRIP solution, being an infrastructure oriented system, requires a specific set-up of the anticipated testing areas. This set-up has been prepared initially on demonstration scenario level (see Fig. 5) and then aggregated for the overall test site, depending the demonstration scenarios that will implement. The lane width in each case is about 3,5m (in all test sites). Marking will be present or not (depending the scenario; for example, for the evaluation of the automated functions, lane markings have to be obstructed at some points). Upon strips installation, a **standardised road marking acrylic cold plastic material with custom**

profile which is abrasion resistant with no length, width or colour restrictions will be applied by SWARCO (project beneficiary).

Fig. 5. Example infrastructure set-up (“Motorway exit scenario”).

D. Validation in real-life traffic conditions

The approach for structuring the evaluation framework and experimental plans of SAFE STRIP has been based on the FESTA methodology, as described in the latest version of the FESTA handbook [2] and the CONVERGE (TR 1101) methodology, as adapted and extended within the INSAFES subproject of PReVENT [3]. In short, upon the definition of the SAFE STRIP functions and their mapping to UC’s and baseline identification, the intended and unintended effects for stakeholders in short/medium and long term have been recognised. The Research Questions/Evaluation Objectives have in turn been defined, mapped to the SAFE STRIP functions and also mapped to Key Performance Indicators (KPI’s), testing rounds and user groups involved. In order to enable testing of the defined evaluation objectives and KPIs, the real-life evaluation scenarios have been structured in a step-wise format for each SAFE STRIP function and on the basis of the project UCs. The experimental conditions for the 1st evaluation round with users have been also defined. Those come together with the specific hypotheses that correspond to KPI for each function, and the recognition of metrics that will be used for their assessment as well as the measuring tools that will be used for this purpose in each case. All those are placed in the context of an overall evaluation plan and its specific experimental design that will be enabled by the specific test infrastructure that will be built (see section V-C). Legal, ethical and Data Management principles will govern the trials, whereas the outcomes of the latest will also feed the impact assessment of the project that is strongly related, of course, to the project functions, their baseline and the research questions and KPI’s. Trials with users in SAFE STRIP can be seen as **small scale Field Operational Trials (FOT) in controlled environment**.

Fig. 6. SAFE STRIP Evaluation methodology.

SAFE STRIP real-life testing will be enabled through the running of traffic scenarios corresponding to the SAFE STRIP applications. It is reminded that SAFE STRIP functions, in their vast majority, are going to be developed as in-vehicle applications for C-ITS equipped and autonomous vehicles as well as mobile applications (delivered through mobile terminals) for non-equipped vehicles. Baseline scenarios in SAFE STRIP are not always possible as they often correspond to situations that are not supported by ITS and it is extremely safety critical to run safety related scenarios in real-traffic without any system support. Therefore, in those situations, statistics will be used, whereas, whenever there is an existing process (i.e. current passage with typical VMS or Toll stations), typical scenarios can be run indeed. Still, there are cases that comparable applications have been developed in the past (with alternative warning systems). In that case and if there is access to the past app, baseline scenarios will be run. Overall 12 SAFE STRIP functions have emerged; either for equipped or non-equipped (some functions are not applicable for both).

The stakeholder chain of SAFE STRIP encompasses apart from road users of all types (drivers, riders, pedestrians) infrastructure operators and authorities, OEM’s, Tier1 suppliers and despite the fact that SAFE STRIP will involve in its last round of real life testing all of them directly or indirectly, it is worth reminding that the SAFE STRIP solution per se is basically an infrastructure based cooperative solution with direct impacts first of all to the road infrastructure holders, as it proposes a cost-efficient solution that aims to impact positively the overall safety, traffic efficiency and environmental status of the traffic network as well as to the drivers and riders of all types of vehicles that benefit from the real-time, safety critical information that is provided to them. Indirectly but equally apparently, SAFE STRIP is expected to affect positively the other road users (i.e. the safety of VRUs such as pedestrians and bicyclists) or other infrastructure operators (i.e. the parking operators, the railway operators, etc.).

The key original project goals related to the key research questions posed (reflecting key expected impacts) constitute a commitment for the project. The key (quantitative) targets of SAFE STRIP are as follows:

- ✓ Reduction of highway fatal accidents \approx 5% - 8%
- ✓ Reduction of fatal accidents at specific traffic scenarios (i.e. merging/intersections) \approx 15% - 30%
- ✓ Cost saving for infrastructure \approx 50%-95%
- ✓ Cost saving for driver/riders \approx 95% - 100%

There are 13 Research Questions (RQ) formulated for the overall evaluation of SAFE STRIP cooperative solution. Research Questions standing also as Evaluation Objectives have been mapped to the Key Performance Indicators (KPI’s) of the project and the SAFE STRIP functions. The RQ and their relevant KPI’s are as follows [4]:

RQ1: Does the system function as expected under realistic conditions (according to specs but also according to user perception)? **KPI’s:** False/missed/delayed alarms, accuracy of vehicle positioning, correctness/accuracy/reliability/personalization of warnings (in terms of content and time), performance enhancement (for existing apps working alternative systems), Automotive Safety Integrity Level (ASIL), acceptance, trust, workload, perceived value of service, interoperability.

RQ2: Does the system function as expected under realistic conditions when more than one SAFE STRIP functions are running concurrently in the user's terminal (according to specs but also according to user perception)? **KPI's:** False/missed/delayed alarms, accuracy of vehicle positioning, correctness/accuracy/reliability/personalization of warnings (in terms of content and time), performance enhancement (for existing apps working alternative systems), ASIL, acceptance, trust, workload, perceived value of service, interoperability.

RQ3: What are the impacts on safety and mobility? **KPI's:** self-explanatory and forgiving roads, driving performance/behaviour, travel behaviour, driver/rider comfort-support in driving task through reliable personalised warnings, perceived societal expectations, readiness to unexpected traffic incidents, equity in roads, impacts on non-users (e.g. VRUs).

RQ4: What are the impacts on traffic efficiency? **KPI's:** traffic flow, traffic volume/density, accessibility.

RQ5: What are the impacts on environment? **KPI's:** Greenhouse emissions, noise, energy saving, fuel consumption.

RQ6: What is the impact on infrastructure operation? **KPI's:** implications in strategic management of national pavement network upon SAFE STRIP penetration, investments on installation and maintenance of costly infrastructure elements (VMS, toll stations).

RQ7: What is the expected user uptake of the system? **KPI's:** cost-effectiveness of the system, acceptance.

RQ8: What are the implications in automated driving in specific? **KPI's:** Robustness of automated driving functions, frequency for the driver having to take back control of the vehicle, driver comfort, advancement of SAE level.

RQ9: What is the expected contribution of SAFE STRIP in C-ITS overall penetration? **KPI's:** Cost-effectiveness of the system, acceptance, innovation & added value.

RQ10: What is the expected contribution of SAFE STRIP in European competitiveness? **KPI's:** New markets/existing markets growth.

RQ11: What are the implications on standards, legislation and regulatory framework? **KPI's:** Readiness to adopt SAFE STRIP – changes required, data protection.

RQ12: What are the implications for policies & business models? **KPI's:** Predicted penetration/user uptake, user expectations, pricing models, policy decisions, authorities' implications.

RQ13: What are the implications on society? **KPI's:** Road safety, QoL, environment, enforcement, sustainable mobility, rehabilitation costs.

Research Questions have been also translated to intended effects for all the different stakeholders in short and medium/long term, whereas, next to them, as it is the case with all novel technological solutions, the Consortium has recognised some unintended effects that may also emerge during evaluation. The mapping to Michon levels [5] (strategic, tactical and operational) and the affected stakeholders of the value chain has been also determined. Those have fed the research questions and the specific experimental hypothesis generation that is described per evaluation scenario. The most important intended effects are the ones on the expected increase of traffic safety, "equity"

in roads and the reduction of manufacturing, operational and maintenance cost for operators. Still, there are unintended effects with regard to overconfidence of road users due to overreliance to the system, excessive information/warning workload during driving, not smooth interaction with other vehicles of surrounding traffic, especially upon creation of new lanes/corridors for automated vehicles as well as the fact that will require changes in the business routines of infrastructure operators. [4].

E. Experimental planning

The 1st round of user trials (to be conducted in the context of the 3rd validation round of SAFE STRIP overall as it is depicted in Fig.3) will run in each participating test site with 10 drivers, who will test the in-vehicle and mobile functions for passenger cars, 3 (different to the previous) drivers, who will evaluate the autonomous functions (a different driver will be "in control" and the other 2 will be passengers), 10 riders, who will test the in-vehicle and mobile functions for motorcycles and 3 representatives from operators (motorway and parking). In a similar way, the 2nd round of user trials (to be conducted in the context of the 4th validation round as shown in Fig.3) will run in each participating test site with the double amount of drivers and rides (20 and 20 respectively), 10 representatives from operators and 3 (different) drivers, as in the first round, to evaluate the autonomous functions. The user trials of the 4th round will be complemented and concluded with focus groups at each test site that will be conducted on-site with key stakeholder representatives from all the SAFE STRIP value chain: drivers, riders, infrastructure operators, parking operators, authorities, Tier 1 suppliers, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs). 29 key evaluation scenarios (with a series of sub-scenarios) have emerged for the 1st round of user trials, based on the Use Cases, so as to accommodate the system performance and the driver response – behavior to it. For each scenario, the experimental conditions have been defined as well as the baseline scenario, whenever applicable. In addition, for each scenario, the applicable Research Questions, the hypotheses to be tested, the measures, the relevant steps of scenario, the frequency of logging, the success target and the ITS Stations that will participate for logging have been defined. There are also cross UCs evaluation scenarios; scenarios combining different functions of SAFE STRIP and serving the purpose of evaluating **Research Question 2** which concerns the concurrent operation of functions under the operation of the SAFE STRIP Decision Support System which operates as HMI manager.

The guideline given to the drivers and riders that will run the traffic scenarios is that they should drive normally and in the safest way possible - as they would in real life - with only two recommendations: 1. To enter the test area with the recommended speed (that is always denoted in experimental conditions for each scenario) and maintain it – if nothing prohibits it – as average speed as much as possible. 2. To react normally – as they would in a real life situation – to the notifications, warnings and recommendations as they will be provided by the system.

Whereas the users will be provided with the scope of the test and, as such, the description of the system they are going to evaluate, they will not be given specific instructions about the messages that they will receive from the system or the

events that will trigger those messages, as this would add bias to the real-life tests.

The experimental design that will be applied in the 1st round of user trials will be within-subjects design, meaning that all drivers/riders that will try all scenarios (assigned to them) will run the exact same traffic scenarios with SAFE STRIP in-vehicle applications, the corresponding ones with SAFE STRIP mobile applications, and, whenever it is applicable/existing, they will also run the baseline scenario. This study is a 2x4 design with 2 independent variables (technical performance and user performance) and 4 levels (baseline-if existing, equipped, non-equipped and autonomous) for the two independent variables common across testing all services. Type of vehicle (passenger car and PTW) are not common across all evaluation scenarios and, hence, are not included as an overall independent variable. Users will be clustered in 6 experimental groups and 1 control group, namely: **Experimental Group 1:** Drivers (10) of equipped passenger demonstrators; **Experimental Group 2:** Drivers (same 10) of passenger vehicles using their mobile terminal (smart phone); **Experimental Group 3:** Riders (10) of equipped PTW demonstrators; **Experimental Group 4:** Riders (same 10 as above) of PTW's demonstrators; **Experimental Group 5:** Drivers (3, one in control by rotation) driving the automated functions in the VALEO demonstrator; **Experimental Group 6:** Infrastructure operators (2 representatives per test site) involved in the evaluation of scenarios corresponding to them. Those will not be involved actively; will oversee the process and give their feedback through the subjective measuring tools; **Control Group:** Each driver testing the evaluation scenarios corresponding to each function will run also the corresponding control scenarios whenever existing, meaning whenever baseline does not originate from literature and traffic statistics (which is the case for the most scenarios in SAFE STRIP though). Each driver/rider will run each evaluation scenario (including the baseline whenever existing) – according to the above clustering – in 3 iterations. The events triggered have been denoted in each evaluation scenario. Participants will be matched across all functions, as not all users will test all functions. Matching will be based at least on selecting potential individual based on gender, age group, driving/riding experience (km driven per year and frequency on weekly basis), literacy and driving/riding profile. In addition, the order of trips, regardless of condition, will be counterbalanced to avoid order effects and over-familiarisation, and consequent desensitization of participants. The latter holds true for drivers and not for road infrastructure operators. The 1st round of trials is seen by the Consortium among other as a “rehearsal” for the larger scale trials that will follow in the 2nd round. As such, the mobile applications that will run in mobile terminals, ergonomically located on-board for safety reasons – will be provided by the Consortium (which will not be the case for the 4th round most probably). Also, although the project demonstrators are in principle meant to be the equipped demonstrators; still will be also used as non-equipped demonstrators in the 3rd round (with V2X deactivated as the drivers/riders will be provided with the messages in their mobile terminal).

F. ITS Logging Mechanisms

In order to log the metrics that are denoted for each evaluation scenario, there will be specific logging mechanisms (ITS-Log modules) that will be built in each

main end of the overall system (infrastructure, cloud, vehicles, mobile devices). Overall, there are two types of direct (raw) or derived (pre-processed) measures that will be logged; driver performance data and system performance data. Driver performance data will be logged either on-board (for vehicle apps running with the equipped demonstrators) or on device (mobile terminals of the users for the mobile apps). System performance data will be logged in different phases of the scenario running in different ends of the system, namely in the RSB, in the C-ITS-S and the application servers that will communicate with it, also in vehicles' OBU and in mobile terminals. The ITS-Log modules (ITS-LM) that will be built in the project will have a common structure and will be commonly applied in all those different ends of the system in order to allow the processing and consolidation of the test results analysis phase. The most critical parameter for the logging mechanism is the accurate time synchronisation. For this reason the GPS timestamp is selected as time reference for all the ITS devices and modules that have access to GPS signal. For the rest modules without GPS reference, the Network Time Protocol (NTP) synchronisation mechanism will be used. As a huge amount of data will be produced in runtime, the ITS-LM has to be designed very carefully, in order to log only the data that are useful for the evaluation process and to discard everything else.

VI. CHALLENGES & NEXT STEPS

SAFE STRIP is in the middle of the 3rd evaluation round and is getting prepared to pave towards the 1st round of user trials. Nevertheless, the key challenge of the project is to achieve an as much as possible equal delivery of services for both equipped and non-equipped vehicles, including also vehicles that are very difficult to equip with rich on-board sensorial platforms, like PTW's. In terms of the system deployment, standardisation and acceptance from road operators are the key decisive factors, while the most significant challenge lies with the energy sustainability of the solution in order to allow such a lifetime that will be indeed cost-efficient.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work presented in this manuscript is realised in SAFE STRIP project which has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement n° 723211).

REFERENCES

- [1] New Market Research on Global & China ADAS Industry, Chisult Insight, 2015
- [2] “FESTA Handbook Version 6 - Updated and maintained by FOT-Net (Field Operational Test Networking and Methodology Promotion)”, December 2016.
- [3] Bekiaris, E., Gemou, M., D60.4: Validation Plan, INSAFES – INtegrated SAFETy Systems, <http://www.prevent-ip.org/insafes/>, February 2008
- [4] Gkemou, M., Deliverable D6.1: Initial report on pilot framework and plans, SAFE STRIP (SAFE and green Sensor Technologies for self-explaining and forgiving Road Interactive aPplications) project, G.A. 723211, www.safestrip.eu, November 2018
- [5] Michon, J. A. (1985). A critical view of driver behaviour models: what do we know, what should we do? In: L. Evans and R. C. Schwing (Eds.). Human Behaviour and Traffic Safety, pp. 485-524. New York: Plenum Press.